

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN

F.D.Ikramova

F.A.Sultonbekova

Department of General Surgery and Transplantology, Andijan State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18478358>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29st January 2026

Accepted: 30th January 2026

Online: 31th January 2026

KEYWORDS

The aim of this study is to analyze the diagnosis and treatment of UC in pregnant women and to discuss optimal treatment methods taking into account the impact on the fetus and potential complications

ABSTRACT

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory bowel disease characterized by colonic mucosal lesions and a recurrent nature. In pregnant women, the diagnosis and treatment of UC require a special approach due to potential risks for both the mother and fetus.

The aim of this study is to analyze the diagnosis and treatment of UC in pregnant women and to discuss optimal treatment methods taking into account the impact on the fetus and potential complications.

Materials and Methods: We analyzed data from 36 patients with UC seen in gastroenterology and obstetrics departments. Patients ranged in age from 22 to 38 years, with a mean age of 30 years. They were divided into four groups. The first group consisted of 14 women whose pregnancy triggered the onset and progression of the disease. Two patients experienced pregnancy toxicosis. All women in this group delivered healthy babies. The patients were then followed for two to seven years. Their ulcerative colitis was relatively mild: intestinal lesions were limited to the distal section, and no signs of disease progression were noted. Our observations indicate that ulcerative colitis that develops during pregnancy, which apparently serves as the trigger, usually has a milder course. The second group included 10 women whose ulcerative colitis was triggered by an induced abortion. Eight of these women developed chronic, relapsing colitis, while two had a relatively mild course. It should be noted that two women subsequently had pregnancies and births that did not cause exacerbations of the disease. The third group consisted of 8 patients with long-term (2-12 years) ulcerative colitis, for whom pregnancy sometimes worsened the disease. According to the literature, such women constituted the majority. Pregnancy and childbirth did not significantly affect the course of colitis in 4 of the women in this group. One woman experienced a mild relapse in the postpartum period. One patient died shortly after childbirth due to a severe exacerbation of ulcerative colitis and its complications.

Group 4 included 4 patients for whom pregnancy improved the severity of clinical manifestations of the disease to such an extent that these women could be considered cured: they experienced stable remission of colitis after pregnancy and childbirth. Thus, it is possible to observe a correlation between the severity of ulcerative colitis and the timing of its onset relative to pregnancy. It is most mild if it develops during pregnancy. If colitis developed several years before pregnancy, relapses during pregnancy are usually mild, and in some cases, persistent remission occurs after childbirth. Colitis that develops after childbirth is most severe. Induced termination of pregnancy can be a trigger for the development and recurrence of colitis.

Results and Discussion.

The study results showed that diagnosing UC in pregnant women requires a comprehensive approach. The most effective methods are colonoscopy (unless contraindicated), stool analysis, and a complete blood count. During pregnancy, it is important to avoid excessive invasiveness, which in some cases limits the use of colonoscopy in the first trimester.

For the treatment of UC in pregnant women, medications that do not adversely affect the fetus are preferred. 5-aminosalicylates (mesalazine) are considered safe and effective first-line agents. The use of corticosteroids is limited to severe exacerbations of the disease. Immunosuppressants and biological therapy can be used in severe cases, but require special caution. The study found that the most common complications in pregnant women with UC are malnutrition, dehydration, anemia, and preterm birth. However, with timely intervention, most women have good outcomes, including the birth of healthy babies.

These results indicate that adequate treatment of UC in pregnant women requires ongoing monitoring and a personalized approach. It is important to consider both the severity of the disease and the state of the pregnancy. The primary focus should be on minimizing risks to the fetus. 5-Aminosalicylate therapy, combined with dietary modification and adherence to a regimen, allows for effective disease control, reducing the risk of complications.

One important aspect is the need to monitor the condition of the mother and fetus, especially in severe cases, which may require the use of immunosuppressants or biologics. The prognosis for the mother and child with

Literature:

1. Левитан М.Х., Смесо́ва Р.В. Неспецифический язвенный колит и беременность. *Врач. дело.* 1981; 3: 29–32.
2. Korelitz B. Pregnancy, Fertility and Inflammatory Bowel Disease. *Am J Gastroent* 1985; 80 (5): 365–70.
3. Грейналь З.А. Диагностика язвенного колита у беременных. Экстрагенитальная патология и беременность. Саратов, 1992; с. 74–6.
4. Косулин В. Х., Патогенетическая терапия неспецифического язвенного колита. *Врач. дело.* 1986; 3: 59–62.
5. Окорочков А.Н. Лечение болезней внутренних органов. Минск: Высшая школа, 1995; 1: 522.

